

The Hand of Antwerp: A Dataset of Middle Dutch Deeds (1300-1355) connected to Jan van Boendale

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The boundary between administrative and literary writings is seldom more blurred than in *Jans teesteye*. This literary work of the influential Middle Dutch author Jan van Boendale (c. 1280-1351?) opens as follows (vs. 1-8):

Alle die ghene die dit werc	To everyone who
Sien lesen ende horen	sees, reads, or hears this work
Die gruetic Jan gheheten Clerc	I greet you, Jan, called the clerk,
Vander Vueren gheboren	born in Tervuren
Boendale heetmen mi daer.	where they call me Boendale.
Ende wone te Andwerpen nu	I now live in Antwerp
Daer ic ghescreven hebbe menech jaer	where I have written for several years
Der scepenen brieve dat segghic u	the deeds, that is what I tell you.

Boendale states that he has written the Antwerp deeds – aldermen’s letters often recording property transactions – for several years. He reaffirms this in the opening verses of the work, which echo a typical opening formula of Middle Dutch deeds (vs. 1-2). His position as a clerk is further confirmed in the Antwerp municipal accounts (Gordeau 2020). Though he must have mastered the administrative language, the extent to which it appears in his literary works has not been systematically investigated, and the evidence remains anecdotal (Reynaert, 2002; Van Oostrom, 2013).

This is remarkable given that Boendale was also an exceptionally prolific *literary* author (Reynaert, 2002; Van Oostrom, 2013). He produced a substantial oeuvre for a lay audience, including patricians and aristocrats, contributing significantly to the development of an emerging lay culture in the Dutch vernacular (Appelmans, 2002). Although the precise delineation of his oeuvre remains debated, it is consistently associated with the so-called ‘Antwerp School’, a group of eleven interrelated works composed in early fourteenth-century Antwerp. These texts are moralistic, didactic and historiographic, reflect similar norms and values, and contain recurring phrases, creating a tight intertextual network (e.g. De Vries, 1844; Reynaert, 2002; Snellaert, 1869; Vandyck, 2025). Boendale certainly authored at least part of the Antwerp School, and recent scholarship favours the maximalist interpretation that he authored the entire corpus (Gordeau, 2020; Vandyck, 2025).

Developing a dataset of digitized and transcribed Antwerp deeds provides an opportunity for a systematic comparison of Boendale’s administrative and literary works. Our central question is inspired by the notion of creative concurrence: the idea that all works populating an author’s worktable influence each other (van Hulle, 2021). Perhaps Boendale wrote some

verses for his literary works at his municipal desk? Scholarship has traditionally divided Boendale's writings strictly into 'administrative' and 'literary', but these likely exist on a continuum rather than forming a clear division. Using the dataset developed for this project, this paper aims to investigate whether – and to what extent – Boendale's literary works display features of an administrative register.

Dataset

The collected dataset comprises entries of 514 deeds written in Antwerp in Middle Dutch between ca. 1300 and 1355, when Boendale was active as a municipal clerk. We limited the corpus to Middle Dutch documents to allow direct comparison with Boendale's literary writings. Compiling an exhaustive catalogue of the deeds is challenging, as many relevant archival holdings are incompletely or incorrectly catalogued. Our catalogue thus aims to be as comprehensive as possible. The dataset includes three metadata fields for each deed – date, repository, and a unique identifier – and each document will be linked to a digital reproduction as well as two transcriptions (Tab. 1).

Our dataset builds on a handlist compiled by former archivist Jos Van den Nieuwenhuizen. Archivist Michel Oosterbosch further enriched this handlist with metadata and a few more entries. Of the 453 deeds relevant to us, cross-referencing with a handlist by Godfried Croenen yielded 55 extra entries. We retrieved six more deeds during the process and added those too, resulting in a collection of 514 deeds in total. 470 of them include an image and are thus most relevant – it was not feasible to digitise the remainder of the deeds within the scope of the project. There are five different sources of facsimiles for the documents. The core is formed by the reproductions assembled by Van den Nieuwenhuizen, which were scanned at the Antwerp State Archives in 2020 under the direction of Oosterbosch. Other reproductions were made by Chris Dewulf, Kamiel Temmerman, FelixArchief and Stadsarchief Mechelen. Some deeds are available in multiple digital facsimiles, which we linked in the dataset by assigning a unique identifier to each deed. The "Final" column contains the best image for each deed, renamed after the unique identifier.

We transcribed all deeds manually and diplomatically following the guidelines in Haverals and Kestemont (2023). We trained a Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) model based on our transcriptions on Transkribus, obtaining a CER of 2.62%. The model will be made available publicly upon publishing the final dataset. To expand the abbreviations in the diplomatic transcriptions, we are currently in the process of finetuning the PIE lemmatizer on our corpus, previously optimized for this task by Haverals and Kestemont (2023). We will share the full dataset – including scans, metadata, and both transcription layers – and the abbreviation solver publicly on Zenodo as soon as they are finalised. The dataset can already be explored and downloaded via a GitHub page, which was made with Necturus (Shahidzadeh Asadi, 2025).¹

¹ <https://mikekestemont.github.io/deeds-of-antwerp/#/collection/1>

ID	Date	Repository	Shelfmark	Transcription_norm	Transcription_dipl	Image_Archive	Image_Temmerman	Image_DeWulf	Image_Oosterbosch	Final	Illegible?
01_09_1331-01	1-9-1331	OCMW	Infirmierie Klapdorp	01_09_1331-01.xml	01_09_1331-01.xml				KM_C3350i20102713520.jpg	01_09_1331-01.jpg	
01_09_1331-02	1-9-1331	ABA	Kartuizers	01_09_1331-02.xml	01_09_1331-02.xml		1-9-1331-Kart.JPG		KM_C3350i20102713521.jpg	01_09_1331-02.jpg	
01_01_1332-01	1-1-1332	OCMW	Infirmierie Klapdorp	01_01_1332-01.xml	01_01_1332-01.xml				KM_C3350i20102812531.jpg	01_01_1332-01.jpg	
03_01_1332-01	3-1-1332	RAA	Pitzemburg	03_01_1332-01.xml	03_01_1332-01.xml	03_01_1332-01.jpg				03_01_1332-01.jpg	

Tab 1.: Excerpt of the metadata, with columns showing the unique identifier, date, repository and shelfmark, and the different transcriptions and images. “Final” refers to the best image, renamed after the ID of the deed.

Wj Willem drake en jan vanden W'ue scepenen jn antw'pen maken cont . dat vore ons q^m arnoud lieden en lijsbeth sijn wetteleke wijf metden seluen arnoute horen wetteghen man en montbore . en gauen en droeghen op den brude'n vanden diedschen huise van pitsenborch in mechelne hoer huis en hoer hof . met al dat daertoe hoert ghestaen bid' butenst' vesten tussche claedorp en kijpdorp met den bogarde en lande daer bi ghelegghen neffens de veste en daertoe al hoer goed rurende en onrurende dat si beide laten selen na hoer lijf bouen haer vtlede en hoer scout . teheffene en te ghebrukene den vorseiden goedshuise deen heleft na den liue des eens van hen tween . en dand' heleft na den liue des anders van hen tween die langst leuen sal . En dese ghifte daden de vorseide man en wijf in recht' aelmoesenen om gode en in vorm van testamte . In kennensse van desen lren . beseghlt met onsen seghlen . Ghegheuen int jaer ons he'n alsin screef . M . CCC . achte en derttech des woensdaegs vore sente Jans dach in midden somere

Fig. 1: Deed kept in Stadsarchief Mechelen (RAA, Pitzemburg) dated 17-06-1338 alongside its manual diplomatic transcription. Based on the dating of this hand, it could be Jan van Boendale's.

Intertextuality

The deeds' transcriptions will enable us to detect the degree of administrative language in Boendale's literary works. These analyses still have to be performed, but the methods have already been developed during earlier research. We aim to computationally retrieve intertextualities – parallel phrases – between the deeds and Boendale's literary works, using the method outlined by Kestemont (2025), which yielded successful results on Boendale's

oeuvre in recent work (Vandyck, 2025).² In order to retrieve parallel phrases between documents, the nearest neighbour of every *lemmatised* phrase or line will be identified.³ The line then is retrieved if the similarity exceeds a previously defined similarity threshold, thus optimally separating identical from differing lines. Kestemont calibrated this threshold based on intertextual phrases manually identified in previous research. Table 2 shows some parallel lines retrieved from *Jans teesteye* and *Lekenspiegel*, two texts generally ascribed to Boendale. We will apply this same method on the deeds corpus and on Boendale’s literary works. Furthermore, we will apply a bag-of-words analysis to compare the vocabulary used in the deeds with Boendale’s oeuvre, and a control corpus of contemporaneous authors, enabling us to investigate whether and how Boendale employed a more professional register.

Tokens <i>Lekenspiegel</i>	Tokens <i>Jans teesteye</i>	Lemmas <i>Lekenspiegel</i>	Lemmas <i>Jans teesteye</i>	Distance
Sal men gaen daer toe / Wijsljic ende met maten	Salmen gaen daer toe / Wijsselijc ende met maten	zullen men gaan daar toe / wijselijc en met maat	zullen men gaan daar toe / wijselijc en met maat	0
Elc mensche die sal / Gode minnen bouen al	Elc mensche die sal / Gode minnen boven al	elk mens die zullen / NOU-P minnen boven al	elk mens die zullen / NOU-P minnen boven al	1,11E-16
Nieman doeden noch verslaen / Gheen valsch orconde doen verstaen	Nieman doden noch verslaen / Gheen valsche orconde doen verstaen	niemand doden noch verslaen / geen vals oorkonde doen verstaan	niemand doden noch verslaen / geen vals oorkonde doen verstaan	1,11E-16
Ende oec niet stelen wats ghesbiet / Nieman doeden noch verslaen	Ende oec niet stelen wats ghesbiet / Nieman doden noch verslaen	en ook niet stelen wat geschieden / niemand doden noch verslaen	en ook niet stelen wat geschieden / niemand doden noch verslaen	2,22E-16
Want soe die nideghe langher leeft / Soe hi meer onwils heeft	Want so die nideghe langher leeft / So hi meer sijns onwillen heeft	want zo die nijdige lang leven / zo hij meer onwil hebben	want zo die nijdige lang leven / zo hij meer zijn onwil hebben	0,004635

Tab. 2: Parallel lines retrieved between two of Boendale’s literary works (Vandyck 2025).

References

- Appelmans, J. (2002). Van Thomas’ bijen tot Jans teesteye. De Brabantse historiografen en hun didactische bekommernis (dertiende en veertiende eeuw). In R. Bauer (Ed.), *In de voetsporen van Jacob van Maerlant: Liber amicorum Raf De Keyser: Verzameling opstellen over middeleeuwse geschiedenis en geschiedenisdidactiek* (pp. 256–283). Leuven University Press.
- De Vries, M. (1844). *Der leken spiegel. Leerdicht van den jare 1330*. Du Mortier en Zoon.
- Gordeau, E. (2020). Boendale en de koning van Engeland. *Tijdschrift Voor Nederlandse Taal- En Letterkunde*, 136(4), 210–223. <https://doi.org/10.5117/TNTL2020.4.002.GORD>

² Boendale’s entire oeuvre is included in the digitally available Corpus Middle Dutch (INT, 2021). See Vandyck (2025) for a description of the data.

³ The texts are lemmatised using the model *hug-tdn-1400-1600* on the platform GaLAHad (INT, 2025).

- Haverals, W., & Kestemont, M. (2023, December 6). *The Middle Dutch Manuscripts Surviving from the Carthusian Monastery of Herne (14th century): Constructing an Open Dataset of Digital Transcriptions*. CHR 2023: Computational Humanities Conference, Paris.
- INT. (2021). *Corpus Middelnederlands* [Computer software]. Dutch Language Institute. <http://hdl.handle.net/10032/tm-a2-j6>
- INT. (2025). *Hug-tdn-1400-1600 (model)* [Computer software].
- Kestemont, M. (2025). Zwerfverzen. De computationele detectie van intertekstualiteit in de Middelnederlandse epiek. *Tijdschrift Voor Nederlandse Taal- En Letterkunde*, 141(2), 87–125.
- Reynaert, J. (2002). Boendale of ‘Antwerpse School’? Over het auteurschap van Melibeus en Dietsche doctrinale. In W. van Anrooij (Ed.), *Al t’Antwerpen in die stad. Jan van Boendale en de literaire cultuur van zijn tijd* (pp. 127–157). Prometheus.
- Shahidzadeh Asadi, N. (2025). *eXtant-CMG/Necturus-Viewer-Compact: V0.1.0* [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15472466>
- Snellaert, F. A. (1869). *Nederlandsche gedichten uit de veertiende eeuw van Jan van Boendale, Hein van Aken e.a.* M. Hayez, Drukker der Koninklijke Akademie.
- Temmerman, K. (2025). *In Search of Boendale’s Hand: A Stylometric and Paleographic Study of 14th-Century Antwerp Charters* [Master Thesis]. University of Antwerp.
- van Hulle, D. (2021). Creative Concurrence. Gearing Genetic Criticism for the Sociology of Writing. *Variants*, 15–16, 45–62.
- Van Oostrom, F. P. (2013). *Wereld in woorden. Geschiedenis van de Nederlandse literatuur 1300-1400*. (4th edn). Bert Bakker.
- Vandyck, C. (2025). The One and Only? Authorship Verification on Jan van Boendale and the Middle Dutch Antwerp School. *Anthology of Computers and the Humanities*, 3, 166–188. <https://doi.org/10.63744/hhieMxHypx67>

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